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Report on the Foodborne Pathogens (FBPs) detected in metagenomics datasets by in silico analysis

Workpackage 2 of JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE

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D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.2

REPORT ON THE FBPS DETECTED IN METAGENOMICS DATASETS BY IN SILICO ANALYSIS

**This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – PARASite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation**

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>)

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Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE–WP2 NGS-based genomics and metagenomics

WP Leader: Yannick Blanchard, ANSES; Deputy WP Leader: Simone M. Cacciò, ISS

Task:

**JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP2-T2- In silico analyses of metagenomes for detection of
foodborne parasites (protozoa and helminths)**

Task leader: Frits F.J. Franssen, RIVM; Deputy Task Leader: Yannick Blanchard, ANSES.

1. Background

The PARADISE project aims to deliver informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for the food-borne parasites *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Using genomics and metagenomics, the project is generating much needed data to enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis for development and testing of improved strain-typing schemes. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices are under development and validation. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches to control *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in the European food chain. Within WP2, the main objectives were: 1) to generate novel genome data from selected isolates of *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* in WP2-T1; 2) to use in silico approaches and a referenced database to interrogate available metagenomes to detect foodborne parasites in WP2-T2; and 3) to use amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics approaches to detect target parasites using spiked food matrices in WP2-T3.

This report deals with the WP2-Task2 “In silico analyses of metagenomes for detection of foodborne parasites (protozoa and helminths)”.

2. Introduction

Amplicon-based and shotgun-based metagenomics approaches have been used for taxonomic profiling of bacterial and viral communities present in different matrices (faeces, other biological samples, environmental and food samples). However, these studies often overlooked the presence of eukaryotic organisms, including parasites. The detection of parasitic sequences in metagenomics datasets is obviously possible, but requires to test analytical pipelines in terms of the specificity and sensitivity they can provide. In the context of WP2-T2, this has been addressed by 1) interrogating publicly available metagenomes for the presence of specific parasites, and 2) performing simulation (spike) experiments. Due to the complexity of the issue, a decision was taken to focus on the main pathogens at the heart of the Paradise project, namely *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*.

3. Analysis of public metagenomes

3.1 Calf gut samples

Using the metagenomic pipeline, we were able to identify metagenomic projects in the public database MG-RAST in which *Cryptosporidium parvum* was detected in four different sites within the calf small intestine. This finding enabled evaluation of the pipeline performance and sensitivity/specificity. Our metagenomic pipeline identified 3095 *C. parvum* reads in project mgm4537108.3, compared to 3080 identified by MG-RAST. We showed that the use of the whole parasite genome yields high sensitivity but low specificity, whereas specificity is improved by the use of signature signatures. The results of this analysis have been published in *Frontiers in Microbiology* (doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.622356).

3.2 Water samples

A metagenome dataset from a hydrothermal vent project (mgm4448187.3) was selected and confirmed to be free of both *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* sequences. The dataset consisted of 231246 reads (average length, 334 bp) generated using the 454 technology. It was then spiked with ten *C. parvum* and ten *G. duodenalis* sequences, which were randomly extracted from the respective reference genome present in a public database (VetPathDB). The pipeline identified the 10 spiked sequences of either parasite, therefore showing high efficiency and specificity.

3.3 Vegetable matrices

We analysed shotgun metagenomics data from three romain lettuce samples (A, B and C), which were the suspected source of infection during a *C. parvum* outbreak that occurred in Sweden (Ahlinder et al., Food and Waterborne Parasitology, 26:e00142, 2022). In the original investigation, the presence of the pathogen in these samples was confirmed by PCR and further explored by shotgun metagenomics at very high sequencing depth (10^8 reads). The authors used BWA to map the sequence reads to the *C. parvum* IOWA reference genome, and reported the presence of 4219, 307 and 249 unique reads in samples A, B and C, respectively. In our analysis, based on the metagenomic pipeline (based on Kraken2 with Braken), the number of reads identified as *Cryptosporidium* spp. was 3121, 2602 and 465, while that specifically assigned to *C. parvum* was 78, 102 and 100, in samples A, B and C, respectively. However, none of the reads could be confirmed as *C. parvum* by BLAST analysis (Table 1). This shows that taxonomic classification based exclusively on read mapping with BWA generates false positive results, and that confirmation of reads by BLAST against the non-redundant NCBI database is necessary.

Table 1. Number of reads assigned to *Cryptosporidium* spp. or to *Cryptosporidium parvum*, and number confirmed as *C. parvum* by BLAST in three metagenomes derived from romain lettuce.

Sample	N of reads passing QC (% of total)	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>C. parvum</i>	N of reads confirmed as <i>C. parvum</i> by BLAST
BV286	138729248/ (35,9%)	3121	78	0
BV287	165350248 (46,0%)	2602	102	0
BV288	247707572 (54,6%)	465	100	0

4. Simulation experiments

To determine the influence of material of eukaryotic origin on the detection of eukaryotic parasites, a metagenome project that investigated Arugula plants (MG-RAST, mgm4551355.3) was selected. This dataset was comprised of 28557634 reads and did not contain any *Cryptosporidium* or *Giardia* sequences. The dataset was spiked with 2500 reads from a *Cryptosporidium parvum* whole genome sequencing (WGS) experiment, or with 625 reads from a *Giardia duodenalis* WGS experiment (both generated by WP2-T1). The unspiked metagenome, the spiked metagenome and the spiked reads

alone were then analyzed using the metagenomic pipeline with Kraken as phylogenetic identifier, and BLAST searches were used to confirm the identity of the reads. The results are presented in Tables 2 and 3. For *Cryptosporidium*, 2092 reads were identified as *C. parvum*, of which 2067 were confirmed using NCBI BLAST. For *Giardia*, 566 reads were identified as *G. intestinalis*, of which 380 were confirmed using NCBI BLAST. Importantly, reads were assigned to either parasites also in the unspiked metagenome; this is likely due to the presence of DNA sequences that are conserved among eukaryotes, i.e., ribosomal sequences.

Table 2. Results of the simulation experiment in which 2500 *Cryptosporidium parvum* reads were spiked into the mgm4551355.3 metagenome.

Sample	N of reads passing QC (% of total)	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>C. parvum</i>	N of reads confirmed as <i>C. parvum</i> by BLAST
Unspiked metagenome	28253230 (98.9%)	481	15	0
Spiked metagenome	28255624 (98.9%)	2806	2092	2067
Reads only	2394 (95.8%)	2325	2077	2067

Table 3. Results of the simulation experiment in which 625 *Giardia duodenalis* reads were spiked into the mgm4551355.3 metagenome.

Sample	N of reads passing QC (% of total)	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>Giardia</i> spp.	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>G. intestinalis</i>	N of reads confirmed as <i>G. intestinalis</i> by BLAST
Unspiked metagenome	28253230 (98.9%)	153	121	0
Spiked metagenome	28253230 (98.9%)	597	565	380
Reads only	459 (73.4%)	443	443	379

5. Conclusions

We investigated various public metagenomes available in the MG-RAST database, and defined optimized strategies that help to overcome the issue of specificity, particularly when the metagenomes are derived from material of eukaryotic origin (e.g., plant). We also performed simulation experiments by spiking pathogen-free metagenomes with known numbers of NGS-derived reads of *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis*. We conclude that in order to avoid false positive results and wrong inferences, results from kmer analyses (e.g., Kraken) or read mapping to a reference genome (e.g., BWA) need to be systematically confirmed by BLAST searches against a non-redundant database. Indeed, sequence

conservation among eukaryotes (e.g., at the level of the ribosomal locus) will lead to incorrect assignments, as shown by detection of reads of (putative) parasite origin in metagenomes that are free of these targets. Finally, we showed that the use of signature sequences can increase the specificity of detection, although at the cost of a lower sensitivity.